

Adapted Concern Assessment Framework for risk benefit communication - test version

EFSA Working Group on Social Research Methods and Advice

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TEST VERSION

ADAPTED CONCERN ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK FOR USE IN RISK BENEFIT COMMUNICATION PLANNING

Working document for testing of risk benefit communication planning tools related to future requests for risk benefit assessments that EFSA receives

1. BACKGROUND

The EFSA Scientific Committee is in the process of revising its 2010 Guidance on Risk Benefit Assessment of Food (RBA).¹ The Terms of Reference of the revised guidance document indicated that it “includes advice on how social science can inform communication of human health RBA”. A section on Risk-Benefit Communication was included in the draft Revised Guidance on Risk Benefit Assessment of Food, made available for public consultation in February-March 2024. This document was prepared by the EFSA Working Group on Social Research Methods and Advice². It describes one of the supporting tools for risk benefit communication planning identified in the draft Guidance: Concern Assessment.

EFSA’s approach to risk communication planning and strategy development (Vrbos et al., 2023), follow the structure of the International Risk Governance Center (IRGC) conceptual framework for understanding risk governance (Florin and Bürkler, 2017; Florin and Parker, 2020). The IRGC framework covers the entire risk analysis process and includes various steps and cross-sectional aspects:

1. Pre-assessment covers the identification and framing of the problem;
2. Appraisal concerns the assessment of the technical and perceived causes and consequences of the risk-benefit;
3. Characterisation and evaluation refer to making a judgment about the risk-benefit and the need to manage it;
4. Management indicates the process of deciding on and implementing risk management options.

Given EFSA’s remit as food safety risk assessor, the available tools cover the first two steps only: Pre-Assessment and Appraisal (Concern Assessment). This document focuses on the **Draft Concern Assessment framework** for risk benefit communication planning.

¹ Self-tasking mandate proposed by the Scientific Committee on the update of the EFSA Guidance for the Risk Benefit Assessment of foods -

<https://open.efsa.europa.eu/question/EFSA-Q-2022-00211>

² <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/science/scientific-committee-and-panels/comco#working-groups>

2. APPRAISAL – CONCERN ASSESSMENT

According to the IRGC framework, the concern assessment should examine i) stakeholders' opinions, values, and concerns about the risk; ii) cognitive heuristics and biases that play a role; iii) potential constraints; iv) social reaction to the risk; v) role of institutions and media in tackling public concern; vi) possible controversies and conflicts (Florin and Bürkler, 2017).

Social research data, either through primary or secondary data collection, provides an understanding of the characteristics of the target population, in terms of awareness of the issue, self-reported knowledge and objective knowledge, risk perception, attitudes, and behavioural intentions. These are to be complemented by media and social media listening that allow grasping information on the volume and sentiment of public discourse around the topic (see Vrbos et al., 2023). These methods support the identification of the perceived characteristics of the information source, as they provide data on, e.g., what are the most used and most trusted information sources about the topic. An additional step in the risk-benefit concern assessment is to identify the characteristics of the trade-off that consumers are going to face. For instance, it could be a trade-off between personal health and well-being (e.g., taste vs health), or between personal economic interest and food characteristics (e.g., price vs quality), or between personal preference and societal considerations (e.g., hedonic value vs animal welfare, ethics, environment).

As illustrated in the literature review on the Communication of food-related health risks and benefits (ICF, 2023), consumers make trade-offs around health, environmental, economic and social factors based on food information. These trade-offs are often made even when the perceived risks of negative consequences are low. The decisions made often consider many factors at once, rather than being a simple balance between two implications (such as health versus cost). Trade-offs may result in decisions that negatively impact consumer health and can be based on minimal information, and so it could be argued that ensuring the public has access to full, accurate information can help consumers to make healthier decisions around consumption.

Once all these data are gathered, a value of concern is calculated based on public's knowledge and perception of the topic. While the original model explained in Vrbos et al. (2023) considers only risk perception, a modified version of the concern assessment that considers benefit perception is proposed.

The value of concern is obtained positioning the topic on a two-axes graph with Knowledge on the x-axis and Perception on the y-axis. "Knowledge" includes four types of information gathered through the assessment: 1) self-reported awareness; 2) self-reported knowledge; 3) objective knowledge; 4) social media volume. Based on the findings of the assessment, a value of -1 (low), 0 (medium), or +1 (high) is assigned through expert judgment to each type of information. For the social media volume, the tool used by EFSA for social media listening provides the exact number of posts on a given period, therefore that number is used to categorise the volume as low, medium or high. The resulting average of the assigned numbers provides a measure of the knowledge about the topic.

The same system is applied for "Perception" which includes four types of information as well: 1) self-reported risk-benefit trade-off; 2) self-reported importance; 3) self-reported interest; 4) social media sentiment. Mirroring the process explained above for "Knowledge", a value of -1 (low), 0 (medium), or +1 (high) is assigned to each type of information. For risk-benefit trade-

off, a value of -1 is assigned if the benefits outweigh the risks, a value of 0 indicates that there is a balance between risks and benefits, while a value of +1 stands for higher risks than benefits. For the sentiment, the tool used by EFSA for social media listening provides the information of the sentiment on a given period, which can be green (positive), orange (neutral) or red (negative).

The intersection between Knowledge and Perception results in a four-quadrants system, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Model for risk-benefit perceptions and social concerns assessment based on a two-axes paradigm measuring knowledge and perception of a food-related topic, including risk-benefit trade-offs.

3. ADAPTED CONCERN ASSESSMENT

This version is adapted from the list of factors to take into account for risk communication detailed in EFSA et al. (2021) and the concern assessment framework described in Vrbos et al. (2023).

The following tables provide an overview of factors that can influence individuals' risk and benefit perception in the field of food safety and that need to be considered for risk and benefit communication.

TABLE 1 PERCEIVED HAZARD CHARACTERISTICS

FACTORS	SUB-FACTORS	DIRECTION OF INFLUENCE ON:	
		RISK PERCEPTION (↓ = DECREASE ↑ = INCREASE)	BENEFIT PERCEPTION (↓ = DECREASE ↑ = INCREASE)
DREAD	Controllable	↓	↑
	Voluntary	↓	↑
	Easy to reduce / mitigate	↓	↑
	Equal distribution of risks / benefits	↓	↑
	Fatal	↑	↓
	Potentially catastrophic	↑	↓
	Threat to future generations	↑	↓
FAMILIARITY	Known	↓	↑
	Observable	↓	↑
	Delayed consequence	↓	↑
	Immediate consequence	↑	↓
SEVERITY	Non-severe	↓	↑
	Severe	↑	↓
NATURALNESS	Natural	↓	↑
	Non-natural / man-made	↑	↓
EXPOSURE	Low number of people	↓	↑
	High number of people	↑	↓
MAGNITUDE	Low probability	↓	↑
	High probability	↑	↓
LEVEL OF CERTAINTY	Low certainty	↓	↑
	High certainty	↑	↓

INTRINSIC PROPERTIES OF FOOD	Tasty / High hedonic value	↓	↑
	Healthy	↓	↑
	Affordable	↓	↑
	Safe	↓	↑
	Nutritious	↓	↑
	Traditional	↓	↑
	Local	↓	↑
	Convenient	↓	↑
	Appealing	↓	↑
	Ethical towards humans, animals, or environment	↓	↑

TABLE 2 INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS

FACTORS	SUB-FACTORS	DIRECTION OF INFLUENCE ON:	
		<i>RISK PERCEPTION</i> (↓ = DECREASE ↑ = INCREASE)	<i>BENEFIT PERCEPTION</i> (↓ = DECREASE ↑ = INCREASE)
PERSONALITY TRAITS	Food (technology) neophobia	↑	↓
	Disgust sensitivity	↑	↓
COGNITION	Overconfidence	↓	↑
	Optimistic bias	↓	↑
EMOTIONS ("AFFECT HEURISTIC")	Negative emotions /affect	↑	↓
	Positive emotions /affect	↓	↑
DIRECT EXPERIENCE	Negative experience	↑	↓
	Positive experience	↓	↑

TABLE 3 PERCEIVED SOCIO-CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS

FACTORS	SUB-FACTORS	DIRECTION OF INFLUENCE ON:	
		RISK PERCEPTION (↓ = DECREASE ↑ = INCREASE)	BENEFIT PERCEPTION (↓ = DECREASE ↑ = INCREASE)
SOCIAL AMPLIFICATION	Dramatisation	↑	↓
	Dispute	↑	↓
	Stigmatisation	↑	↓
SOCIAL NORMS	No conflict	↓	↑
	Conflict	↑	↓
LEVEL OF PUBLIC CONCERN	Low concern	↓	↑
	High concern	↑	↓
SOCIAL TRUST	Low trust	↑	↓
	High trust	↓	↑

TABLE 4 PERCEIVED INFORMATION CHARACTERISTICS

FACTORS	SUB-FACTORS	DIRECTION OF INFLUENCE ON:	
		RISK PERCEPTION (↓ = DECREASE ↑ = INCREASE)	BENEFIT PERCEPTION (↓ = DECREASE ↑ = INCREASE)
TRANSPARENCY	Low transparency	↑	↓
	High transparency	↓	↑
CONSISTENCY	Conflicting with individual's perception	↑	↓
	Consistent with individual's perception	↓	↑
TRUST	Untrustful source	↑	↓
	Trustful source	↓	↑

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